

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MEASURED YIELD STRESS AND HARDNESS IN ALUMINIUM MATRIX COMPOSITES REINFORCED WITH MoSi₂

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ABSTRACT

Six AA6061/MoSi₂/15p composites were processed with controlled reinforcement size and distribution. Deviation of measured tensile yield stress from the empirical value of H/3 in solutionized condition has been quantified by a factor that takes into account the value of the coefficient of variation of mean near-neighbour distances, COV_λm.

Keywords: Aluminium matrix composite, powder metallurgy, yield stress, hardness, particle distribution

INTRODUCCION

Aluminium-based metal matrix composites (AMCs) with particle reinforcement have been developed as structural materials due to their high strength to weight ratio and isotropic properties, superior, in general, to those of conventional aluminium alloys. Another attractive aspect of particle reinforced AMCs is that conventional metal working processes can be used [1,2]. Powder metallurgy is one of these techniques, whose main characteristic is that the spatial distribution of the particles is normally more homogeneous than that obtained through casting methods. However, clustering may still occur on a smaller scale because of static charges acting on particle surfaces, or due to geometrical reasons when there is a large difference between matrix and reinforcement particle sizes [3]. High-energy ball milling has been used to improve particle distribution throughout the matrix [4,5] because fracturing and cold welding of the powder particles occur, giving rise to the reinforcement particles being well embedded into each aluminium particle. Furthermore, the high degree of deformation involved may reduce matrix grain size to nanometer level and produce a very fine distribution of oxides depending on the processing parameters [6].

Hardness tests are routinely used as simple and effective non-destructive means to determine the mechanical quality of AMCs, which depends, among other factors, on matrix microstructure (grain size, precipitates) and reinforcement (size, volume fraction, distribution) [7-9]. Yield stress ($\sigma_{0.2}$) and hardness (H), in mechanically alloyed aluminium alloys, are related by the relationship $\sigma_{0.2}=H/3$ [10]. This equation has proven to be valid in relating compressive $\sigma_{0.2}$ of, for example, Al-15 at.% MgB₂

composites [11]. However, the same equation can lead to large overestimation of tensile 0.2% yield stress, especially when the strength of the Al matrix is relatively low as occurred in some 2080/SiC/10p and 2080/SiC/20p particle reinforced AMCs [12].

In the current work, six 6061/MoSi₂/15p solutionized composites have been processed by powder metallurgy with varying reinforcement size and distribution with the aim of checking to what extent the empirical $\sigma_{0.2}=H/3$ relationship is valid for these materials, and in the case it fails, whether a simple relationship between macroscopic hardness and yield stress can be found. For this purpose, the effect on tensile yield stress and hardness of both reinforcing particle size and distribution, which certainly plays a significant role during indentation and tensile loading, has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The starting matrix material was 6061 aluminium alloy powder, with particle diameter <50 μm and composition in % mass: 0.45 Si, 0.96 Mg, 0.27 Cu, 0.0023 Mn, 0.16 Cr, 0.15 Fe, balance Al. Two initial ranges of irregular shaped MoSi₂ particles were selected as reinforcement: <3 μm (composites group 1) and 10-45 μm (composites group 2). The 6061 powder was blended with 15% volume of MoSi₂ by three methods: wet blending (1W), rotating cube (2C), and planetary ball milling operating at 200 rpm for 4 hours (1M(4h) and 2M(4h)) and 10 hours (1M(10h) and 2M(10h)). The blends were consolidated by extrusion in a horizontal direct hot extrusion press at a temperature of 450°C. The consolidated materials were solution heat treated at 520°C for 0.5 hours and water quenched. Table 1 lists the materials prepared, together with MoSi₂ particle size ranges (D_{R0}), blending methods and their corresponding codes.

Microstructural characterization was performed on cross sections of solutionized samples by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) using a FEG-JEOL 6500 microscope. Polished specimens were prepared by standard metallographic techniques without any chemical etching. Back-scattered SEM micrographs at the same magnification of composite cross sections are shown in Figure 1 [13]. Qualitatively, it is evident that final MoSi₂ particle size, D_{RF} , decreases with milling time, and that MoSi₂ distribution is quite homogeneous. Image analyses of the composites were performed by Image-Pro Plus software on back-scattered electron images to determine reinforcement size and distribution. The degree of particle clustering was also quantified by CProbe software to measure the coefficient of variation of the mean near-neighbour distance (COV_{λ}) [14].

Vickers hardness of solutionized consolidated materials was measured on cross sections of polished samples. At least 5 indentations were performed for each material by applying a load of 1 kg during 15 seconds. The results are presented with an accuracy of ± 0.03 GPa.

Tensile testing was performed on solutionized samples at room temperature with a strain rate of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ using a universal testing machine. The tensile samples were cylindrical, with gauges of 3 mm diameter and 20 mm length, and were machined with the tensile axis perpendicular to the extrusion direction. At least three samples were tested in each case. Results are presented with an accuracy of ± 10 MPa.

Table 1. Materials, MoSi₂ particle size ranges (D_{R0}), blending methods and codes.

6061/ MoSi ₂ /15p	D_{R0} (μm)	Blending method	Code
Group 1	< 3	Wet blend	1W
		Ball mill: 4 h	1M(4h)
		Ball mill: 10 h	1M(10h)
Group 2	10-45	Rotating cube	2C
		Ball mill: 4 h	2M(4h)
		Ball mill: 10 h	2M(10h)

Figure 1. Back-scattered SEM micrographs of cross sections of AA6061/MoSi₂/15p composites at the same magnification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measured values of Vickers hardness and 0.2% yield stress ($\sigma_{0.2\text{exp}}$) are given in Table 2. Within each composite group, the ball milling process produced an increase in the mechanical strength of the materials. With regards to the hardness, it increases between 16 and 22% when comparing non-milled materials with 4h-milled ones, and 4h-milled materials with 10h-milled ones. With regards to the experimental 0.2% yield stress, its increase is more pronounced, being of around 20% when comparing non-milled with 4h-milled materials, and of around 35% when comparing 4h-milled and 10h-milled materials. As was reported in a previous work [13], hardness of solutionized composites follows a Hall-Petch mechanism, and it can be rationalised as the sum of the hardness of the alloy matrix with the same matrix grain size, and a term H_R that is the

remaining contribution of MoSi₂ reinforcement to hardness and rather independent of particulate size and distribution.

To gain insight into the relationship between the experimental composites yield stress $\sigma_{0.2exp}$ and their microstructures and to investigate to what extent the empirical relationship $\sigma_{0.2H}=H/3$ is valid in the present case, $\sigma_{0.2exp}$ has been plotted in Figure 2 as a function of hardness for the six AMCs. Although it may be possible to find a unique relationship between hardness and composite strength, it is evident that data points are far below the expected values from the equation $\sigma_{0.2H}=H/3$, represented by the dotted line and listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Vickers hardness, Hv; experimental, $\sigma_{0.2exp}$, expected, $\sigma_{0.2H}$; and normalized 0.2% yield stress, $\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H}$, of 6061/MoSi₂/15p composites

Code	Hv (GPa)	$\sigma_{0.2exp}$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{0.2H}=Hv/3$ (MPa)	$\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H}$
1W	0.90	203	300	0.678
1M(4h)	1.04	249	347	0.717
1M(10h)	1.24	341	413	0.828
2C	0.82	204	273	0.747
2M(4h)	0.96	243	320	0.759
2M(10h)	1.17	329	390	0.843

Figure 2. Experimental yield stress vs. hardness

To study to what extent $\sigma_{0.2exp}$ differs from the expected value $\sigma_{0.2H}$, the ratio $\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H}$ has been considered, Table 2, which is the experimental value normalized by the one expected from $Hv/3$. For each group of composites, $\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H}$ approaches to the unit as time of ball milling increases. This indicates that the longer the milling time, the more accurately could be use hardness to estimate composite tensile strength. In order to try to relate this behaviour with microstructural features, the ratio $\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H}$ has been

plotted against reinforcement particle size and other parameters that are related with particle distribution. With regards to reinforcement size, listed in Table 3, it is evident that there is no relationship between MoSi₂ size and the ratio $\sigma_{0.2\text{exp}}/\sigma_{0.2\text{H}}$, Figure 3. Moreover, not even the expected tendency of larger particles giving rise to lower yield stress is fulfilled (which is mainly due to the higher facility of larger to fracture during the tensile test), as resulted from the comparison of 1M(4h) with 2M(10h), that have the same particle diameter but clearly different yield stress.

Table 3. MoSi₂ particle size after blending (D_{Rf}), and cell area, local area fraction, mean near-neighbour distance and their coefficient of variations (COV).

Code	D_{Rf} (μm)	Cell area	COV_{ca}	Local area fraction	COV_{laf}	Mean near- neighbour distance (λm)	$\text{COV}_{\lambda\text{m}}$
1W	1.36	2.60	0.77	18.94	0.82	1.97	0.55
1M(4h)	0.58	1.40	0.96	13.84	0.87	0.96	0.51
1M(10h)	0.35	1.14	0.97	15.17	0.85	0.83	0.41
2C	17.01	8.38	0.63	15.09	0.81	19.99	0.41
2M(4h)	1.38	3.03	0.98	12.26	0.94	1.47	0.46
2M(10h)	0.59	1.79	0.92	12.40	0.89	0.98	0.41

Figure 3. Normalized yield stress versus reinforcing particle size.

In order to quantify the homogeneity of the distribution, a finite-body tessellation of the microstructure was created. Several parameters related to the MoSi₂ particle distribution have been determined and listed in Table 3. These are the cell, or polygon, area and its coefficient of variation COV (defined as the standard deviation divided by the mean value), the local area fraction, i.e. the fraction of area that occupies every particle in its corresponding cell and its COV, and the mean near-neighbour distance that describes the mean value of the average of the distances of every particle to its first neighbour (λm) and its COV. The value of COV is particularly useful to normalize measurements and the COV value of a certain parameter of the tessellation generally will decrease with decreasing homogeneity of the distribution [15].

In Figure 4, the normalized experimental 0.2% yield stress has been plotted against the six distribution parameters described above. It is manifest that none of them allow to derive a simple relationship. Only in the case of COV_{λ_m} , Figure 3f, all the points fit very well to a single straight line of negative slope, regression coefficient of 0.989, when the material with the largest reinforcing size is neglected (2C), so that $\sigma_{0.2exp}$ value can be related to its hardness by the equation:

$$\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H} = 1.29 - 1.13 COV_{\lambda_m}$$

So, deviation of tensile yield stress in solutionized condition from the empirical value of $H/3$ can be quantified by a factor that takes into account the particle distribution through the value of COV_{λ_m} . (Study of why composites with large reinforcing particles do not follow this trend is in progress.). Yang et al. [15] showed that COV_{λ_m} is particularly sensitive and effective in characterizing particle clustering and relatively insensitive to particle volume fraction, size, and shape. This result is in agreement with the fact that an heterogeneous distribution usually promotes lower yield strength owing to higher strength concentration at agglomerates [16]. Moreover, it indicates that composite tensile strength can be better estimated by hardness measurements when the reinforcement distribution is more homogeneous, the latter measured through COV_{λ_m} . Finally, it highlights that in order to try to find a straightforward hardness–strength relationship in particle- reinforced metal matrix composites as the behaviour exhibited by conventional monolithic materials, it has to be taken into account other factors besides particle size that are related to reinforcing particle distribution.

Figure 4. Normalized yield stress $\sigma_{0.2exp}/\sigma_{0.2H}$ as a function of reinforcing particle distribution parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

To try to explore the correlation between hardness and tensile properties of particle reinforced AMCs, six 6061/MoSi₂/15p composites with varying reinforcement sizes and distributions have been processed by powder metallurgy.

As occurred to other composites, hardness test significantly overestimates the yield strength of the 6061/MoSi₂/15p composites.

The more homogeneous is the composite particle distribution, the more the $\sigma_{0.2exp}$ approaches to the value of $H/3$.

A straightforward relationship between hardness and $\sigma_{0.2exp}$ has been found by taking into account the degree of homogeneity of reinforcement distribution, measured through COV_{λ_m} . This allows to use hardness measurements to estimate composite tensile properties, at least for small particle sizes.

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